

Frequency Of Stress Urinary Incontinence With Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease In Men; A Cross Sectional Survey

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 20, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: December 21, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Stress Urinary, Hospital, Teaching, Pulmonary Disease</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7464944</p>	<p>Objectives: To measure the frequency of stress urinary incontinence in men with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.</p> <p>Material and Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional survey was done in Ghurki Teaching Trust Hospital, and Gulab Devi Hospital, Lahore from September 2019 to February 2020. A total of 217 men patients with diagnosed chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and ages 30-50 years fulfilling inclusion criteria from two tertiary care hospitals of Lahore were taken for the proposed study by non-probability convenience sampling. Incontinence Questionnaire-Urinary Incontinence Short Form (ICIQ-UI SF) was used to measure severity and frequency of urinary incontinence. The validity and reliability of this questionnaire (ICIQ-UI SF) was currently established by Burge, A.T, et al. The results were presented in the form of descriptive analysis.</p> <p>Results: Urinary incontinence was present in 78.8% (171/217 patients), 21.2% experience urine leakage with physical activity or exercise, 20.7% have urine leakage while coughing or sneezing. Stress urinary incontinence was showed the prevalence 41.9%. Most of patients' experiences incontinence once a day 43.3%, 18% have several times a day, 8.8% have two to three times a week, and 7.4 % have once a week and 3% have all the time. 52.5% showed a small amount of urine leakage, 23.0% showed moderate urine leakage and only 3.2% of patients showed a large amount of urine leakage. On inquiring from patients about how much, leaking urine does interfere with your everyday life according to zero to 10 rating scale, a large number of patients marked no interference but some patients marked 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 with the percentage of 8.8%, 9.7%, 12.0%, 14.7%, and 7.8% respectively. Urinary incontinence was showed that having great interference :Chronic obstructive, pulmonary disease; Bronchitis; Urinary incontinence and affects quality of life of patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease but it is still unclear in this work.</p> <p>Conclusion: It was concluded that urinary incontinence is highly associated with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Patients experience a small amount of urine leakage on daily basis, which is affecting their quality of life. Urinary incontinence linked with coughing, sneezing, physical activity of exercise.</p>

Introduction

Urinary incontinence (UI) is the most common problem, but less reported, and according to estimation, 200 million people affected by UI and the values increased to 423 million by 2018 worldwide. The problem increases with age. Although it is not fatal but very unpleasant and disturbing, socially and psychologically depressing and affecting quality of life (QOL). Risk factors can be old age, constipation, high body mass index (BMI) and chronic cough due to any respiratory problem.^{1,2} Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a complex condition and has multiple components; symptoms include dyspnea, exercise intolerance increases with disease progression, chronic cough and urinary incontinence.³

Involuntary leakage of small amounts of urine associated with exertion, such as sneezing or coughing causing an increase in intraabdominal pressure called stress UI; the urgency is a sudden desire to pass urine, which is difficult to control. The symptoms can range from mild leaking to uncontrollable wetting.⁴ Incontinence occurs due to multiple reasons like hypermobility of bladder neck, disturbance in closure of urethral sphincter or absence of contraction of detrusor muscle.⁵

Urinary incontinence is classified into: frequency, stress incontinence, urge incontinence or mixed incontinence and post micturition dribble.⁶ UI a common health problem increases with age having a frequency of 15% over 70 years of age. Both COPD and UI affect quality of life and disturb daily activities as compared to healthy

individuals of the same age. In comparison to general risk factors, including age and obesity, a variety of particular factors may increase the possibility of UI in individuals with COPD. Impaired sphincter control is associated of dyspnea, which is a characteristic feature of dyspnea in patients with COPD. Another widely accepted possible cause is persistent cough, which puts extra pressure on the pelvic floor or may cause the UI. In people with advanced COPD, physical dysfunction due to dyspnea was also prevalent and raises the chances of UI development.⁷

A survey on medications that may lead to lower urinary tract side effects noted inhaled tiotropium seems like the only pulmonary (inhalant) drug prescribed for COPD which typically causes of the urinary tract retention. Which can affect continence due to the impact on bladder function, urinary excretion change, mental retardation, and dysfunction of the functional capacity using bathroom.⁴

Current study was found out the frequency of stress urinary incontinence in men with COPD and how did it effect their quality of life. Least work has been done regarding UI in men and the frequency of UI in individuals with COPD is mostly unexplored in clinical research and often underestimated in clinical practice in our setting.

Material And Methods

Sequel to acquiring approval from Institutional Review Board (IRB) of University of Health Sciences (UHS) Lahore, subject descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out from Ghurki Teaching Trust Hospital, and Gulab Devi Hospital, Lahore from September 2019 to February 2020. With a written informed consent, a sample of 217 men patients (calculated by WHO sample size calculator, $n = Z^2_{1-\alpha/2} P (1-P) / d^2$, whereas population proportion was 0.17%, absolute precision 0.05% and confidence level 95%)⁸ confirmed diagnose COPD with age 30-50 years, were included in this study. Patients with kidney diseases, any other reason of incontinence and patients with lower urinary tract infections were excluded from the study.

The data was collected by using Incontinence Questionnaire-Urinary Incontinence Short Form (ICIQ-UI SF) questionnaire. The validity and reliability of this scale (ICIQ-UI SF) was currently established by Burge AT, et al.⁷ Non-probability convenience sampling was done for the data collection.

The following procedure was used for evaluation of the patients: ICIQ-UI SF was used as a measurement to determine the urinary incontinence in COPD. Patients selected according to inclusion exclusion criteria. Data collection done by asking questions from the patients verbally with their consent. Questionnaires filled after explain each and every question to the patient and asked for their sincere and serious marking about the options given below every question according to their disease type and severity.

All collected data was entered in computer program statistical package of social science (SPSS) version 23 and analyzed through this very software. The results were presented in the form of descriptive analysis. The qualitative variables were presented as percentages and quantitative variables as mean.

Results

Among 217 patients of urinary incontinence, mean age and standard deviation were 45.78 ± 4.35 with minimum age 30 years and maximum 50 years. Total 78.8% patients of COPD have UI and 21.2% did not have. ICIQ-UI SF questionnaire were measured. Patients with COPD experiences urine incontinence once a day, several times a day, two to three times a week, once a week and all the time were recorded (Table-1). The percentage of frequency of quantity of urine leakage were recorded in patients with COPD (Table-2). On inquiring from patients about how much leaking urine interfere with your everyday life according to 0 to 10 rating scale. Out of 78.8% of patients who have UI with COPD, a large number of patients marked 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 with the percentage of 8.8%, 9.7%, 12.0%, 14.7%, and 8.3% respectively (Table-3). The percentage of frequency "when does urine leak" was recorded (Table-4). Out of 78.8% of patients who had UI, 31.8% showed urine leakage all the time, 21.2% experience urine leakage with physical activity or exercise, 20.7% have urine leakage while coughing or sneezing. Showing the prevalence of stress UI 41.9%.

Table I: How often patient leak urine, n = 217

ICIQ-UI SF questionnaire	Frequency	Percentage
Never	46	21.2
About once a week	16	7.4
Two to three times a week	19	8.8
About once a day	94	43.3
Several times a day	39	18.0
All the time	03	1.4
Total	217	100

Most of the patients with COPD experiences urine incontinence once a day.

Table II: How much urine usually leak, n = 217

ICIQ-UI SF questionnaire	Frequency	Percentage
None	46	21.2
A small amount	114	52.5
A moderate amount	50	23.1
A large amount	7	3.2
Total	217	100

Table III: How much leaking urine interferes with everyday life, n = 217

ICIQ-UI SF quality of life	Frequency	Percentage
0	46	21.2
1	4	1.8
2	10	4.6
3	10	4.6
4	16	7.4
5	15	6.9
6	19	8.8
7	21	9.7
8	26	12.0
9	32	14.7
10	18	8.3
Total	217	100

Table IV: When urine leak, n = 217

ICIQ-UI SF questionnaire	Frequency	Percentage
Never	46	21.2
Leak before toilet	02	0.9
Leak when cough or sneeze	45	20.7
Leak when asleep	01	0.5
Leak when physically active/exercising	46	21.2
Leak when finished urinating and dressed	03	1.4
Leak for no obvious reason	05	2.3
Leak all the time	69	31.8
Total	217	100

Table V: Summary of Urinary Incontinence based on ICIQ

Summary of Urinary Incontinence based on ICIQ		
	Frequency	Percentage
Severity Level		
No Incontinence	60	27.6

Mild Incontinence	60	27.6
Moderate Incontinence	79	36.4
Severe Incontinence	18	8.3
Type of Incontinence		
Not Applicable	46	21.2
Urge Incontinence	3	1.4
Stress Incontinence	91	41.9
Mixed Incontinence	77	35.5

Majority of the subjects found to be with moderate to mild incontinence among whom majority were having stress and mixed type of incontinence. Mild incontinence was significantly associated with stress incontinence while moderate and severe incontinence significantly associated with mixed type of incontinence (p value 0.0001).

Table VI: Summary of Urinary Incontinence based on ICIQ versus Type of Incontinence

Summary of Urinary Incontinence based on ICIQ versus Type of Incontinence							
		Type of Incontinence				Total	P Value
		Not Applicable	Urge Incontinence	Stress Incontinence	Mixed Incontinence		
Summary of Urinary Incontinence based on ICIQ	No Incontinence	46	3	11	0	60	0.0001
	Mild Incontinence	0	0	60	0	60	
	Moderate Incontinence	0	0	20	59	79	
	Severe Incontinence	0	0	0	18	18	
Total		46	3	91	77	217	

Discussion

In our knowledge this is first survey in Pakistan on stress urinary incontinence in men with COPD. The finding of 78.8% of prevalence of UI in men with COPD is relevant to for clinical practice. A large number of patients from the sample collected have urinary incontinence, in 53.5% of patients a small amount of urine is leaking on daily basis and situation is getting worse in some cases.

More patients experience urine leakage all the time or maximum time of the day, some experience urine leakage with cough, sneezing, physical activity or exercise expressing the most common cause of UI associated with COPD. Stress urinary incontinence (SUI) seems to be the most common type of urine leakage in this study. 41.9% patients experience urine leakage with physical activity and exercises or while coughing or sneezing. Battaglia S, et al.,⁴ and Newman DK.,⁹ studies showed increased intra-abdominal pressure causes urine leakage, and stress incontinence.

A study by Burge AT, et al.,⁷ UI is the most common and most neglected complication of COPD, does not cause death but affects QOL of the patients. COPD is progressive and time-consuming disease, rehabilitation is slow. It is not surprising that most patients did not perceive that UI has impact on their QOL. As most of the patients 21.7% marked it is not bothersome but a huge difference is seen when 14.7% of patients marked 9 on 0 to 10 rating scale.

A study conducted by Hrisanfow E, et al.,¹⁰ both UI and COPD are associated with negative psychosocial effects and poorer QOL has been described in men with COPD and UI. Although higher scores were recorded, in this study patients QOL effects with COPD and UI. Although this study was only to determine the prevalence of SUI in COPD men patients.

COPD is associated with a persistent cough that results in the manifestation of stress or damage to the symptom if it already exists. Other symptoms of COPD, such as fatigue and shortness of breath, may slow down patients' movements, and thus make it easier for a small body effort to create an uncontrollable episode. Smoking cigarettes often trigger a cough that increases the pressure on the bladder and lower back, thus increasing the risk of the disease.¹¹ Jelić S, et al.,¹² study results pointed to a significant increase in urinary incontinence in

patients following COPD depletion (78%), similar to our study results of 78.8% of UI prevalence in men with COPD. Schnell k, et al.,¹³ study results showed that 34.9% of COPD patients treated with primary health care were uncontrollable, in contrast to 27.3% of patients who did not have COPD, but were treated for another disease in primary health care.

This study showed a significant association between urinary incontinence based on ICIQ and type of incontinence ($p \leq 0.0001$). Whereas, Hrisanfowe E and Hagglund D, study of 2109 patients aged 40 to 69 confirmed a significant correlation between urinary incontinence and COPD, but not other comorbidities.¹⁰ The quality of life reported by patients should be considered when assessing the state of health as FEV1 is insufficient to assess the clinical severity of COPD.¹⁴ Van Gerwen M, et al.,¹⁵ conducted a study in which all medical records were analyzed from 2001 to 2008 in which they diagnosed common urinary tract infections. It has been shown that this symptom is more common in men when they suffer from heart failure, and in women it is more common when they have diabetes, genitourinary prolapse, asthma and COPD.

This study can help to have concentration and consideration of UI while assessing the patients of UI and improving their QOL by proper treatment protocols. Further work is needed to understand the QOL of patients with UI and how much the disease progression effects on the frequency and intensity of UI.

Conclusion

It is concluded that UI is highly associated with COPD. Patients experience a small amount of urine leakage on daily basis, which is affecting their QOL. UI linked with coughing, sneezing, physical activity of exercise.

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